

ISic1409

I.Sicily inscription 1409

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Megara Hyblaea

Place of origin (modern)

Megara Iblea

Provenance

Between Sortino and Leontini

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Megara Iblea

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140918

1. [— —]ΧΟΓΟ [— — — —]
2. [Ζ] ἡ [σ] α [ς] ἔτη [— —]
3. [—] πρὸ ἰγ' κ [αλ(ανδῶν)]
4. [—]ΕΙΙΥΚΑΙ [— — — —]
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493026

EDCS 39101538

PHI 140918

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0591 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

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